

THE IMPORTANCE OF FORMING MEDICAL LITERACY IN MARRIAGE AGE STUDENTS

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Annotatsiya: The article presents an analysis of the development of medical literacy of students, considering it as a pedagogical problem. Special attention is paid to the levels and factors of medical literacy.

Key words: medical literacy, health, medical culture, medicinal plants, dental method, skills, competence.

Health literacy involves recognizing risk, understanding conflicting information, making health-related decisions, and when health systems, communities, and government policies and structures do not fully meet the needs of the citizen as a patient. requires functional capacity to understand complex healthcare systems and changing 'demand'. Health competencies shape people's behavior and choices, and ultimately their health and well-being. Low levels of medical literacy lead to unhealthy lifestyles, risky behaviors, hospitalizations, and increased health care costs. Data from the European Health Literacy Survey show that 30-40 percent of the population has inadequate or poorly developed health literacy skills. Poor health literacy is characterized by poor health care, low independence, and reduced ability to manage patients' self-care, frequent hospitalizations, and high costs. Improving medical literacy strengthens the ability of individuals and communities to resist negative external influences, helps to overcome social injustices in relation to health, and improves the health and well-being of the population. Medical literacy helps to find solutions to health problems. Medical literacy is primary medical to the population at the political level as well

tries to find solutions in providing assistance. The analysis of scientific medicinal plants shows that the most promising strategies for the development of competence in health issues, health education carried out in institutions of continuing education, secondary special professional colleges, etc. It is based on the cooperation of lim institutions. In the 21st century, social and natural sciences in various countries face problematic situations in making decisions about health. More and more people are being asked to make healthy lifestyle choices and make their own way for themselves and their families through complex environmental and health care solutions, but no one is preparing them for this and does not support them in solving related tasks. In "modern" society, there is an active promotion of an unhealthy lifestyle, and it is becoming more and more difficult to act in health care systems. In the face of global environmental crises, the restoration and prevention of the physical health of the population through natural means and resources, medicinal plants, is becoming more and more necessary. With the development of science and technology, artificial systems, geocenoses and even tools that have a positive effect on health are becoming artificial. In this regard, the possibility of maintaining the health of the future generation and putting it in a systematic way will increase based on the study of medicinal plants carried out in scientific research work. The health of the population develops under the influence of several factors: they include social, economic, environmental, personal characteristics, behavior and other factors. In addition, maintaining health and leaving a healthy, strong generation for the future is the result of a healthy society - a healthy mindset. In this regard, medical literacy is an important factor of health. The analysis and monitoring of the health of more and more countries notes that in the study of medical literacy, the medical literacy in them is different from the social and historical background of the countries. The average adult population of the United States has low levels of medical literacy. . Observations on medical literacy among the PRC population in 2012 showed that 91.2% of the Chinese population had low or low medical literacy. Studies of medical

literacy in European countries have shown that 47% of the population, more than in European countries, have a low level of medical literacy. Low or insufficient medical literacy is a global health concern because a problem. Medical literacy is defined as "... the ability to receive, process, and understand basic medical information, and the ability to understand and analyze medical decisions." Young people are less connected to the health care system and have lower health care costs than older people.

Medical literacy includes three core competencies:

1. Functional competence: this is the ability to agree to doctors, nurses, pharmacists or verbal information, read and understand written sources and act according to the instructions of medical professionals, take medications correctly, and adhere to care. skills are listed.
2. Conceptual competence: a broad range of personal abilities that include lifelong development of health care skills, understanding, evaluating and using health information and concepts, making informed choices, reducing health risks and improve the quality of life.
3. Empowering Health Competence: Strengthening Active Citizenship for Health through Integration.

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